

Foreign and Domestic Agricultural Capital Investments and Agricultural Development Nexus in Nigeria

SALIU ADEJARE, Rauff, Ph.D & OLUWAYEMISI, Odeniyi, Ph.D

^{1&2}Department of Economics,

Federal College of Education (Special), Oyo.

¹rauf.saliu1789@fcesoyo.edu.ng

²odeniye.oluwayemisi3086@fcesoyo.edu.ng

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14885721>

Abstract

Nigeria's agriculture industry, despite abundant resources, is contributing less to the economy due to challenges faced by traditional and smallholder farmers. Specifically, this study compares the effect of foreign and domestic agricultural capital investments on agricultural development in Nigeria. This study therefore employed annual secondary data covering 1980–2023, in Nigeria. This study's adopted the Autoregressive Distributed Lagged Model technique to identify the relationship. The findings of the first objective of remittance inflows (REMIT) revealed a positive but statistically insignificant ($t = 0.4466$, $p > 0.05$) relation with agricultural development in Nigeria. Net Official Development Assistance Received (ODA) established a negative and statistically insignificant relationship ($t = -0.2038$, $p > 0.05$) with agricultural development in Nigeria. The second objective results showed that agricultural research and development was negative but statistically significant links was established with agricultural development ($t = -1.9883$, $p < 0.05$; agricultural subsidy (AGSUB) revealed positive and statistically significant links with agricultural development ($t = 2.4707$, $p < 0.05$); the finding of fertilizer input (FERT) and ratio of irrigated land to total land (IRRIG) are both negative and statistically significant, and rural development result is positive but statistically insignificant related to agricultural development in Nigeria. The study therefore concluded that agricultural development could only be improved if agricultural capital investments are increased and its implementation is monitored in Nigeria.

Keywords: Agriculture Domestic Expenditure, Agriculture Foreign Expenditure, Autoregressive Distributed Lagged Model (ARDL).

1.1 Introduction

Over the years, agriculture has been identified to be a strong pillar in the sustainability of any economy. Agriculture helps to provide food for the citizens of a country. Agriculture helps in the provision of raw materials for industries, employment opportunity in a country and source of income for farmers and it improves the wellbeing of the society at large. To achieve this level of agriculture, investment is needed and in this case government expenditure to achieve this objective. Globally, agricultural sector acts as the catalyst that accelerates the pace of structural transformation and diversification of the economy, enabling the country to fully utilise its factor endowments and depend less on foreign supply of agricultural products or raw materials for its economic growth, development and sustainability (Ishola, et al., 2013).

Government stimulates growth in sectors of the economy such as agriculture, by formulation of policies and direct investments that would impact agriculture directly. The government identifies the areas of concern and makes practical efforts (Onakoya & Somoye, 2013).

Government expenditure is basically purchases made by government for public consumption or investments that are not readily provided for by the private sector but important for the welfare of a nation. It can also be in terms of subsidy for startups to help them grow to a level where they can be self-sustaining. Lawal (2011) defines government spending or expenditure to include all government consumption, investment, and transfer payments. Government can directly influence activities in the agricultural sector, using both capital expenditure and recurrent expenditure directly and indirectly. Capital expenditure involves spending on the building of feeder roads in rural areas, silos, tractors, fertilizers, research and development in agriculture, subsidy to agricultural inputs and other equipment for farmers, resulting in increased output and well-being of people in those areas.

Despite huge resources to finance agriculture at individual household's, agribusiness firms, governments at all levels and internationally, the expected positive effects have not been experienced in Nigeria. Globally, every nation including Nigeria is wary of food scarcity and hence this study.

1.2 Research Objectives

The broad objective of this study is to empirically investigate effect of agricultural spending on agricultural development in Nigeria with a view to specifically determine:

- i. The effect of foreign capital investments on agriculture on agricultural development in Nigeria, and
- ii. The effect of domestic total capital spending on agriculture on agricultural development in Nigeria.

1.3 Research Questions

The following research questions emanate from this study:

- i. to what extent does foreign capital investments in agriculture influences agricultural development in Nigeria.
- ii. to what extent does domestic agricultural total capital spending influences agricultural development in Nigeria.

1.4 Research hypotheses

The following research hypotheses are going to be established or refuted in this study:

H₀: Foreign capital investments in agriculture do not influence agricultural development in Nigeria

H_A: Foreign capital investments in agriculture influence agricultural development in Nigeria and

H₀: Domestic agricultural total capital spendings do not have influence agricultural development in Nigeria.

H_A: Domestic agricultural total capital spending has an influence on agricultural development in Nigeria.

2 Literature review

2.1 Theoretical literature

The idea that economic growth results from internal, rather than external, sources is known as the endogenous growth theory. The theory's foundation is the notion that advancements in human capital, knowledge, and innovation boost productivity, which in turn improves the state of the economy. In addition, the theory sources of growth is from rate of total factor productivity (TFP) which is influenced by technical advancement and economic growth, affecting production per person. Higher economic activity can accelerate process innovation, while economic policies like trade, competition, education, taxes, and intellectual property influence research and development (R&D) costs and benefits according to the theory.

2.2 Empirical Literature

Hussain's (2016) study explores the impact of agriculture aid on agricultural productivity in 77 developing countries from 2002 to 2014. Results show a positive relationship between aid and productivity, but policy indicators show a negative association. The study recommends a 126% increase in agricultural aid to double productivity by 2030. Nomor and Udele's (2024) study on Nigeria's economic growth from 1981-2022 found that agricultural output positively responds to government recurrent agricultural expenditure, while capital agricultural expenditure negatively impacts economic growth. The study suggests that the government should improve monitoring of capital agricultural project funds to ensure overall efficiency.

Sikandar et al. (2021) examined the poverty-agriculture-capital trilemma pattern, revealing that capital inflows impact poverty reduction and agriculture development. They found that increased agricultural exports, foreign direct investment, and migrant worker remittances can improve poverty reduction. Moreover, deeper integration of developing economies into global food supply chains can enhance agriculture. Also, Okorie and Chikwendu's (2022) study on Nigerian agricultural expenditure found that government capital and recurrent expenditures positively impact agricultural sector output. Capital expenditure had a significant impact, suggesting that increased budgetary allocation to the sector could increase output in the long run. The study recommends improving agricultural budget execution through quick passage and timely implementation, and closely monitoring expenditures. Igweze-Ekwunife and Okpala's (2022) study examines the impact of government expenditure on agricultural output in Nigeria from 1986 to 2019. The results show that capital expenditure, domestic savings, foreign direct investment, and commercial bank credit significantly impact agricultural output. The study recommends capital and infrastructural projects, domestic savings mobilization, and mechanized farm tools.

From the extant researches and above stated researches, it has been observed that paucity of research has been carried out on isolating the effect of agricultural foreign and domestic capital expenditure on agricultural development in Nigeria and hence, this study.

3 Methodology

The study therefore used the annual data covering 1980–2023, in Nigeria. Using the Augmented Dickey-Fuller unit root test, the study discovered that variables were stationary at a level and first difference. This study's used the Autoregressive Distributed Lagged Model (ARDL) bounds test technique to identify long and short runs relationships, and conducted diagnostic tests to ensure accuracy. The theoretical framework was developed. The models were specified and sources of data were also highlighted.

The endogenous growth model is the foundation of our investigation. The endogenous growth model focuses on the overall economy's behaviour. If the output takes the simple Cobb-Douglas Production form as:

$$Y = A_t K^{1-\beta} L^\beta \quad 3.1$$

The net national product is represented by Y, the capital stock by K, the labor stock by L, and the technological level by A. Romer (1987a) proposed a model in which A was determined locally by knowledge spillovers after the aforementioned expression failed to explain the disparities in growth rates among the countries.

They proposed that, similar to endogenous growth models, the degree of technology A(t) may vary among states or nations. They proposed that information about A diffuses gradually from high A to low A locations, using the historical beginning distribution of differences in A(t). Since $y = Y/L$ indicates production per worker and $k = K/L$ indicates capital per worker, this would imply that there is underlying variance in A(t) among the states that influences both k and y.

3.1 Specification of models

The framework for aggregate production put out by Fosu and Magnus (2006), Constant and Yaoxing (2010), and Udoh (2011) was used in our analysis. An extension of the traditional production function, which highlights labour and capital as the primary components of production, the aggregate production framework looks at the effects of additional variables like public spending, foreign capital (ODA, remittances), and so forth. The function connecting period t's total output to inputs or components of production has the following general form:

$$Y_t = A_t K^{\alpha-1} L^{\alpha-2} \quad 3.2$$

where Y represents the agricultural sector's total production at time t, as well as the capital stock, labor stock, and Total Factor Productivity (TFP) at that moment. According to Udoh (2011), Lipsey (2001), and Barro (1990, 1991), the total factor productivity (A) may be the mechanism via which government spending affects output growth. Thus, TFP is a function of agricultural public spending (AGPE), agricultural subsidy (AGSUB), and other exogenous factors (C), according to Udoh (2011). We modeled L as the proportion of Nigerian farmers to the country's overall population, where K stands for the farmers' private investment. Because ODA and international remittances can fill the gaps of limited domestic capital in developing nations like Nigeria, they have been shown to address the savings and trade balance (foreign exchange) constraints to agricultural production and growth (Verter, 2017). For this reason, the study included them in the TFP model. In addition to supporting household consumption and livelihoods, remittances (REMIT) can promote longer-term development by funding land purchases, agricultural input purchases, and education (Iheke, 2016).

Thus, the Total Factor Productivity can be modelled as:

$$A_t = f(RANDD_t, AGPS_t, IRRIG_t, RD_t, FERT_t,) \quad 3.3$$

Equation (3.3) can be written explicitly as:

$$A_t = \alpha_3 RAND_t, \alpha_4 AGPS_t, \alpha_5 IRRIG_t, \alpha_6 RD_t, \alpha_7 FERT_t \quad 3.4$$

3.1.1 Effect of Total Domestic Capital Investments On Agriculture On Agricultural Development in Nigeria

In order to achieve the first objective of this study of investigating effect of domestic capital investment on agriculture on agricultural development in Nigeria, are as follows:

$$Y_t = C_t \alpha_1 K_t \alpha_2 L_t \alpha_3 AGPS_t \alpha_4 IRRIG_t \alpha_5 RD_t \alpha_6 FERT_t \tag{3.5}$$

Linearizing equation (3.10) and adding the error term (ε_t), we obtain estimable econometric model as follows:

$$\text{Log}Y_t = C_t + \alpha_1 \text{Log}K_t + \alpha_2 \text{Log}L_t + \alpha_3 \text{Log}RD_t + \alpha_4 \text{Log}AGPS_t + \alpha_5 \text{Log}IRRIG_t + \alpha_6 \text{Log}RD_t + \alpha_7 \text{Log}FERT_t + \varepsilon_t \tag{3.20}$$

As a result, the study used Pesaran et al (2001) autoregressive distributed lag model was employed to establish a long-run effect of domestic capital investments on agricultural development in Nigeria.

The following is the model:

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta Y_t = & \alpha_0 + \sum_{i=1}^p \phi_{1i} \Delta Y_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^{q_1} \phi_{2i} \Delta \text{Log}K_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^{q_2} \phi_{3i} \Delta \text{Log}L_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^{q_3} \phi_{4i} \Delta \text{Log}RD_{t-i} \\ & + \sum_{i=0}^{q_4} \phi_{5i} \Delta \text{Log}AGPS_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^{q_5} \phi_{6i} \Delta \text{Log}IRRIG_{t-i} \\ & + \sum_{i=0}^{q_6} \phi_{7i} \Delta \text{Log}FERT_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^{q_7} \phi_{8i} \Delta \text{Log}Y_{t-i} + \delta_1 \text{Log}K_{t-1} + \delta_2 \text{Log}L_{t-1} \\ & + \delta_3 \text{Log}RD_{t-1} + \delta_4 \text{Log}AGPS_{t-1} + \delta_5 \text{Log}IRRIG_{t-1} + \delta_6 \text{Log}FERT_{t-1} + \delta_7 \text{Log}Y_{t-1} + \mu_t \end{aligned} \tag{3.6}$$

Δ is the difference operator. The coefficients δ_1 to δ_8 indicated the long-run connection, while the equation with sums ϕ_1 to ϕ_8 reflected the model's short-run dynamics. μ_t is the serially uncorrelated disturbance with zero mean and constant variance. After confirming that there is co-integration between the variables, the following long run model for ΔY_t was created

$$\begin{aligned} Y_t = & \alpha + \delta_1 Y_{t-1} + \delta_2 \text{Log}K_{t-1} + \delta_3 \text{Log}L_{t-1} + \delta_4 \text{Log}RD_{t-1} + \delta_5 \text{Log}AGPS_{t-1} \\ & + \delta_6 \text{Log}IRRIG_{t-1} + \delta_7 \text{Log}FERT_{t-1} + \delta_8 \text{Log}Y_{t-1} + \mu_t \end{aligned} \tag{3.7}$$

The variables' lag ordering was selected using the proper Information Criterion to get the optimum ARDL specification structure. The following error correction model was created to foresee the short run dynamics after estimating the ARDL specification and determining the pertinent long run results:

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta Y_t = & \alpha_0 + \sum_{i=1}^p \phi_{1i} \Delta Y_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^{q_1} \phi_{2i} \Delta \text{Log}K_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^{q_2} \phi_{3i} \Delta \text{Log}AGPS_{t-i} \\ & + \sum_{i=0}^{q_3} \phi_{4i} \Delta \text{Log}NAGPE_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^{q_4} \phi_{5i} \Delta \text{Log}REMIT_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^{q_5} \phi_{6i} \Delta \text{Log}LODA_{t-i} + \gamma \text{ECM}_{t-1} \\ & + \mu_t \end{aligned} \tag{3.8}$$

Where the adjustment parameter is assumed to be less than zero and the short run parameters range from ϕ_1 to ϕ_6 . The delayed error correction component, the ECM term, was derived using the estimated co-integration model of the equation. Three tests were run: the serial correlation test, the Jacque-Bera normalcy test, and the heteroscedasticity test. To determine if the model was well described, the Ramsey RESET test was also run. The stability of the long and short run coefficients

and whether the two statistics stayed below the 5% significant threshold were examined using the CUSUM and CUSUMSQ residual equation tests.

3.1.2 *A priori* expectation

It is expected that K is farmer private investment is proxy gross fixed capital formation in Agriculture, L is ratio of farmers' population to total population, AGSUB– Agricultural Credit Guarantee Scheme Fund (proxy for agricultural subsidy), Rural Development proxy by Rural population (% of total population), FERT – Fertilizer, IRRIG - Agricultural Irrigated Land (% of total agricultural land), ODA - Net Official Development Assistance Received (constant 2021), REMIT - Remittance inflows (% of GDP in 2023) are expected to have a positive relationship Y – Agriculture Real Gross Domestic Product per capita is gross domestic product divided by midyear population for it to improve agricultural development.

3.2 Sources of data, description and measurement of variables

This study discusses relevant variables, as detailed in Table 3.1.

Table 3.1 Presentation of variable measurements and sources

Variable	Definition	Measurement	Symbol	Source
Agriculture Real Gross Domestic Product per capita	Value added per worker is a measure of labor productivity —value added per unit of input. Value added denotes the net output of a sector after adding up all outputs and subtracting intermediate inputs. It includes forestry, hunting, and fishing as well as cultivation of crops and livestock production.	Value added per worker	Y	Central Bank of Nigeria Statistical Bulletin (2024)
Farmer Private Investment	Gross fixed capital formation includes land improvements; plant, machinery, and equipment purchases; and the construction of roads, railways, and the like.	Gross Fixed Capital Formation in Agriculture	K	World Development Indicator (2024)
Ratio of Farmers' Population To Total Population	Rural population refers to people living in rural areas as defined by national statistical offices. It is	Rural population (% of total population)	L	World Development Indicator (2024)

		calculated as the difference between total population and urban population.			
Agricultural Subsidy		Funds, grants and supply of inputs to assist agricultural production.	Agricultural Credit Guarantee Scheme Fund (proxy for agricultural subsidy)	AGSUB	Central Bank of Nigeria Statistical Bulletin (2024)
Rural Development		Rural development are ways of allowing the rural areas to develop by providing infrastructure facilities to rural dwellers to boost agricultural production.	Rural population (% of total population)	RD	World Development Indicator (2024)
Fertilizer		Fertilizer as input to farmers	Fertilizers to farmers that are subsidized or free.	FERT	World Development Indicator (2024)
Agricultural Irrigated Land			Agricultural irrigated land (% of total agricultural land)	IRRIG	World Development Indicator (2024)
Net Official Development Assistance Received		Net disbursements are gross disbursements of grants and loans minus repayments of principal on earlier loans.	Net official development assistance received	ODA	World Development Indicator (2024)
Remittance Inflows		When migrants send home part of their earnings in the form of either cash or goods.	Remittance Inflows (% of GDP in 2023)	REMIT	World Development Indicator (2024)
Research and Development in Agriculture		Gross domestic expenditures on research and development (R&D), expressed as a percent of GDP. They include both capital and current expenditures in the four main sectors: Business enterprise, Government,	R&D expenditure in percentage of GDP	RANDD	World Development Indicator (2024)

Higher education and
Private non-profit.

Source: Author’s computation (2024)

4 Empirical results, interpretation and discussion

The study uses unit root tests and structural break tests to analyze variables' stationarity, examining the impact of foreign capital investments and domestic capital expenditures on Nigerian agriculture.

4.1 Unit root results

The findings of unit root tests established a mixture of I(0) and I(1) for the optimal unit root tests with breaks in Table 4.1. In general, the use of Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) as an estimation technique is justified in terms of accuracy, according to Pesaran, Shin, and Smith (2001).

Table 4.1 Optimal Augmented Dickey-Fuller unit root test with structural break

Variable	Level	First Difference	Break Date	Order of Integration
Y	-7.0075**** ^a		2002	I(0)
K		-9.5653**** ^b	2018	I(1)
L		-20.9635**** ^b	1990	I(1)
AGPE		-5.9373**** ^a	1991	I(1)
AGPS		-6.6071***	2006	I(1)
NAGPE		-9.3851 ⁸⁸⁸⁸	2007	I(1)
AGSUB		-9.3769***	2005	I(1)
FERT		-9.5468***	2017	I(1)
IRRIG		-9.3846***	1998	I(1)
ODA	-8.9790***		2006	I(0)
RANDD	-6.5733***		1983	I(0)
REMIT	-7.5846***		2004	I(0)
RD	-13.3613**		1990	I(0)

Note: Intercept = a, Intercept and Trend =b. ADF is Augmented Dickey Fuller unit root tests while ***, ** and * represent 1%, 5% and 10% levels of significance, respectively. I(0) and I(1) represents stationary at levels and first difference respectively.

Source: Author’s Computation (2024)

4.2 Results of the effect of foreign capital investment on agricultural development in Nigeria

Result of ARDL Bounds testing was employed to determine whether or not there was a long-run relationship between the variables of interest. Table 4.2 shows the result of the F-statistic (4.2505), which was larger than the critical values for the upper and lower bounds at the 5% level of significance. It followed as a consequence that the null hypothesis that there was no co-integration has been ruled out completely. It implied that there was long-term relationship between foreign capital investments on agricultural development in Nigeria, as shown below.

Table 4.2 Result on bounds test

F-statistic	4.2505
K	4
Upper Bounds	3.49
Lower Bounds	2.56

NOTE: ***, ** and * represent 1%, 5% and 10% levels of significance, respectively.

K is the number of exogenous variables in the model

Source: Author's computation (2024)

The results of the bounds testing confirmed the model's long-run connection. An autoregressive distributed lags model was used to calculate the coefficients for the short and long periods, respectively. As shown in Table 4.3, the ARDL findings indicated that the coefficient of error correction term was negative and statistically significant at 5 percent significant level, indicating that there was co-integration and a stable long-run connection among the variables. The error correction term coefficient represents the rate at which the condition of equilibrium was being adjusted (-0.3906) and an adjustment speed to long run equilibrium aftershock of 39.06 percent was identified, indicating that the ECT was effective.

The findings on the relationship between the Nigeria's foreign capital investments on agricultural development are shown in Table 4.3 as short-run findings of the link between the variables. The results of the bounds testing confirmed the model's long-run connection. An autoregressive distributed lags model was used to calculate the coefficients for the short and long periods, respectively. As shown in Table 4.3, the ARDL findings indicated that the coefficient of error correction term was negative and statistically significant at 5 percent significant level, indicating that there was co-integration and a stable long-run connection among the variables. The error correction term coefficient represents the rate at which the condition of equilibrium was being adjusted (-0.3906) and an adjustment speed to long run equilibrium aftershock of 39.06 percent was identified, indicating that the ECT was effective.

The findings on the relationship between the Nigeria's foreign capital investments on agricultural development are shown in Table 4.4 as short-run findings of the link between the variables. The short and long runs coefficients of Remittance Inflows (REMIT) revealed a positive but statistical insignificant relation with agricultural development in Nigeria during study's period. Though, the find had a positive link that follow the theoretical proposition but weak. More, REMIT inflow is require to make it impactful on agricultural development in Nigeria. Also, both in the short and long runs Net Official Development Assistance Received (ODA) showed a negative and statistically insignificant relationship with agricultural development in Nigeria given the period under investigation. These did not go in tandem with the theoretical expectation. More need to be done to reverse the situation and make it impactful.

Table 4.3 ARDL short run results of effect of foreign capital investment on agricultural development**Dependent variable Y(1, 0, 0, 0, 0) SIC**

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	133.8486	81.8441	1.6354	0.1104
D(Y)	-0.3907	0.0940	-4.1546	0.0002
D(LnK)	-0.0012	0.3086	-0.0040	0.9968
D(LnL)	-6.8522	4.6466	-1.4746	0.1488
D(REMIT)	0.2528	0.5710	0.4427	0.6605
D(LnODA)	-0.1159	0.5629	-0.2059	0.8380
ECT	-0.3906	0.0726	-5.3804	0.0000
R ²	67%			

NOTE: ***, ** and * represent 1%, 5% and 10% levels of significance, respectively.

Source: Author's computation (2024)

Table 4.4 ARDL long run results of effect of foreign capital investment on agricultural development**Dependent variable Y (1, 0, 0, 0, 0) SIC**

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
K	-0.0031	0.7901	-0.0039	0.9968
LnL	-17.5393	11.3757	-1.5418	0.1316
REMIT	0.6471	1.4489	0.4466	0.6577
LnODA	-0.2967	1.4562	-0.2038	0.8396
C	342.6045	201.4559	1.7006	0.0974

NOTE: ***, ** and * represent 1%, 5% and 10% levels of significance, respectively.

Source: Author's computation (2024)

4.3 Residual diagnostic test results

To evaluate the accuracy and robustness of the estimations, the residual diagnostic test results were presented in Table 4.5. The Jarque-Bera test result showed that the error was not normally distributed based on the results of the normality tests. The model was shown to be free of serial correlation in the Correlogram serial correlation Test at a 5% level of significance, indicating that the null hypothesis of no serial correlation cannot be ruled out. As can be shown in Table 4.5, the heteroscedasticity test did not affect how accurate the computed parameters were. The Ramsey reset's test result was non-significant, which suggested that all of the model estimations were reliable and consistent. To further support the ARDL model's parameter stability, as previously mentioned, the cumulative sum (CUSUM) and cumulative sum squares (CUSUMSQ) of the recursive estimates were generated. Figures 4.3.1 and 4.3.2 show the results of the CUSUM and CUSUMSQ tests, respectively. The results of CUSUM and CUSUMSQ showed that the plotted line fell inside the two vital lines in both CUSUM and CUSUMSQ, indicating that the lines are within 5% critical bounds in both CUSUM and CUSUMSQ, which confirmed that long run coefficients were stable when short run dynamics were taken into consideration. From this point of view, the ARDL model used in the research was strong and reliable.

Table 4.5 Residual diagnostic test results

Correlogram	0.0476 (0.827)
Heteroskedasticity Test (BPG)	0.1891 (0.9649)
Normality Test	338.7034 (0.0000)
Ramsey RESET'S Test	0.0483 (0.8272)

Note: p-values are in the parentheses.
Source: Author's computation (2024).

Figure 4.3.1: Cumulative Sum Test
Source: Author's computation (2024)

Figure 4.3.2 Cumulative Sum Squares Test
Source: Author's computation (2024)

4.4 Results of the effect of domestic total capital spending on agriculture on agricultural development in Nigeria

The second goal of this research is to investigate the impact of domestic total capital spending on agriculture on agricultural development in Nigeria. In this study, domestic capital that are relevant agriculture are used for the study's analyses. According to the literature, such as Alabi and Abu (2020) domestic capital are: Agricultural Subsidy, Rural Development, Fertilizer, Agricultural Irrigated Land and Research and Development in Agriculture.

In order to determine whether or not there was a long-run relationship between domestic total capital expenditure on agriculture and agricultural development in Nigeria given the period under investigation, co-integration test must be conducted for the variables in the models.

The existence of a long-run equilibrium relationship between domestic total capital expenditure on agriculture and agricultural development in Nigeria was studied in this research utilising the bounds testing technique to co-integration, which was applied to the data. The results of Table 4.6 indicated that there were long-term relationship between domestic total capital expenditure on agriculture and agricultural development in Nigeria. Diagnostic tests for the models were also performed as part of the study. The results of the diagnostic tests shown in Table 4.18 confirmed that the model's unbiased parameters were correct.

The findings of ARDL Bounds testing are used to determine whether or not there is a long-term relationship between the variables under consideration. In order to empirically demonstrate the relationship between domestic total capital expenditure on agriculture and agricultural development in Nigeria. Table 4.6 shows that the F-statistic result (2.9770) was greater than the critical values for the upper and lower bounds at the 5 percent significant level, indicating that the F-statistic was significant. Therefore, the null hypothesis that there was no co-integration has been rejected. This demonstrated a long-term relationship between domestic total capital expenditure on agriculture and agricultural development in Nigeria.

Table 4.6 Result on bounds test

F-statistic	2.9770
K	7
Upper Bounds	3.83
Lower Bounds	2.69

NOTE: ***, ** and * represent 1%, 5% and 10% levels of significance, respectively.

K is the number of exogenous variables in the model

Source: Author's computation (2024)

At the end, the results of the bounds tests demonstrated that the models were related in the long term. The autoregressive distributed lag model was used to estimate the coefficients for the short and long runs, respectively. In the autoregressive distributed lag model, the error correction term coefficient was negative and statistically significant, as seen in Table 4.7. The findings also supported the presence of co-integration and the existence of a long-term stable link between the variables studied. Statistics shown that the ECT was statistically significant and negative. The rate of adjustment to equilibrium was represented by the ECT (-0.7299). It was revealed that aftershocks with a frequency of 72.99 percent returned the system to its long-term equilibrium.

Second objective on the relationship between Nigeria's agricultural development and domestic total capital expenditure during the study period are shown in Table 4.7 and 4.8. In relation to the agricultural development in Nigeria under investigation, the short- and long-term coefficients for Farmer Private Investment (K) are both negative and statistically insignificant. This outcome does not meet the expectations of economic apriori. It is implied that the country's degree of agricultural growth decrease as Farmer Private Investment increases over the study period. This indicates that the nation's necessary fixed capital creation mix is either insufficient or has no direct bearing on agricultural development. Likewise, Research and development in Agriculture (RANDD), which is expected to have a positive relationship with agricultural development turns out to be statistically significant but negative. It is implied that the research and development mixes that are currently available do not support the ones that are required for the agricultural development of the Nigerian economy. Both short-term and long-term agricultural subsidies followed the apriopri anticipation of encouraging and noteworthy developments. Given the research period, the degree of agricultural development in the Nigerian economy increased by 136.9% in the short term with a 1% change in agricultural subsidies. In the long run, Nigeria's agricultural development increased by 187.6% in response to a 1% adjustment in agricultural subsidies. Both in the short and long term.

Table 4.7 ARDL short run results of effect of total capital expenditure on agricultural development

Dependent variable Y (2, 0, 0, 0, 1, 0, 0, 0) SIC

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
		1157.88		
C	-1353.475	9	-1.1689	0.2516
Y	-0.7299	0.1582	-4.6139	0.0001
D(LnK)	-1.4801*	0.8159	-1.8140	0.0797
		8984.81		
D(LnL)	-13799.09	0	-1.5358	0.1351
D(LnRANDD)	-			
)	12.6903**	6.0183	-2.1086	0.0434
D(LnAGSUB)	1.3690**	0.6646	2.0596	0.0482
		118.852		
D(IRRIG)	-161.3600	6	-1.3576	0.1847
		9049.47		
D(LnRD)	13884.70	0	1.5343	0.1354
D(FERT)	-0.1595	0.1400	-1.1387	0.2638
D(LnY(-1))	0.4123**	0.1533	2.6893	0.0116
D(LnAGSUB)	0.0731	0.6562	0.1115	0.9120
ECT	-0.7299	0.1263	-5.7775	0.0000
R ²	49%			

NOTE: ***, ** and * represent 1%, 5% and 10% levels of significance, respectively.

Source: Author's computation (2024)

Table 4.8 ARDL long run results of effect of total capital expenditure on agricultural development

Dependent variable LAGPE (2, 0, 0, 0, 1, 0, 0, 0) SIC

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
LnK	-2.0277**	1.0357	-1.9576	0.0596
LnL	-18904.45	11314.76	-1.6707	0.1052
	-			
LnRANDD	17.3855**	8.7438	-1.9883	0.0560
LnAGSUB	1.8755**	0.7591	2.4707	0.0194
IRRIG	-221.0603	160.2016	-1.3798	0.1778
LnRD	19021.73	11397.60	1.6689	0.1055
FERT	-0.2185	0.1948	-1.1216	0.2709

NOTE: ***, ** and * represent 1%, 5% and 10% levels of significance, respectively.

Source: Author's computation (2024)

4.5 Residual Diagnostic Test Results

Table 4.9 shows the results of the residual diagnostic tests performed to account for the estimates' reliability and robustness checks. The results demonstrated that the error was not normally distributed, as shown by the normality tests performed by the Jarque-Bera method. The results of the Serial Correlogram Test also indicated that the models were free of serial correlation at 5 percent significance level, implying that the null hypothesis of no serial correlation cannot be ruled out completely. Moreover, according to Table 4.9, the heteroscedasticity of Breausch-Pagan-Godfrey suggested that the heteroscedasticity test did not pose any danger to parameter estimates correctness. Also, result of the Ramsey Reset's Test was insignificant, which implied that the model estimates were correct and valid. It was also determined that the ARDL's parameters were stable by calculating a cumulative sum (CUSUM) and a cumulative sum square (CUSUMSQ) of the recursive estimates, respectively. The results of the CUSUM and CUSUMSQ tests according to figures 4.4.1 and 4.4.2 revealed that the plotted lines were contained inside the two critical lines in both tests. CUSUM and CUSUMSQ, by implication, showed that the lines were inside the 5 percent critical boundaries. As a result, the stability of the long run coefficients were maintained throughout the short run dynamics. This indicated that the ARDL models used in the research were stable and dependable, as shown by the results.

Table 4.9 Residual diagnostic test results

Correlogram	0.1010 (0.751)
Heteroscedasticity Test (BPG)	0.8946 (0.5490)
Normality Test	65.8069 (0.0000)
Ramsey RESET'S Test	0.6534 (0.4255)

Note: p-values are in the parentheses.
Source: Author's computation (2024).

Figure 4.4.1: Cumulative Sum Test

Figure 4. 4.2 Cumulative Sum Squares Test

Source: Author's computation (2024)

Source: Author's computation (2024)

5. Conclusion

Findings from the first objective about the relationship between foreign capital investments and Nigerian agricultural development. Nigerian agricultural development and the short- and long-run coefficients of remittance inflows (REMIT) had a positive but statistically insignificant relationship agricultural development in Nigeria. The results validated the theoretical premise because of the positive connection. More influx is required for REMIT to have an effect on Nigeria's agricultural development. Nigeria's agricultural development and Net Official Development Assistance Received (ODA) also had a negative and statistically insignificant relationship during the study period, both in the short and long terms. These did not meet the theoretical expectation. More work needs to be done to change things and make a difference.

The results of the second goal examined the connection between Nigeria's agricultural development and domestic total capital expenditure on agriculture. The short- and long-term coefficients for Farmer Private Investment (K) are both negative and statistically insignificant. This outcome does not meet the expectations of economic apriori. It implies that the country's degree of agricultural growth will decrease as Farmer Private Investment increases over the study period. This indicates that agricultural development is not directly related to the nation's required fixed capital creation mix. Likewise, Research and Development in Agriculture (RANDD), which is anticipated to have a positive impact on agricultural development and also contributed significantly.

6 Recommendations

From the findings of the analyses of this study, the following recommendations emerged:

This study recommends that quick passage and prompt implementation of the budgets will increase the execution rate of the agriculture budget. More agricultural subsidies in different forms and types such as agricultural inputs and cash need to be encouraged and monitor to be used to boost agricultural development in Nigeria. More foreign capital need to be solicited and monitor it to be used for agricultural productivity in Nigeria. Public spending on agriculture should be redirected to support investments in rural development, irrigation, and research and development, which currently get smaller financial allocations in Nigerian agricultural budgets.

References

- Barro, R. (1990). Government spending in a simple endogenous growth model. *Journal of Political Economy* 98(5):103– 125.
- Barro, R. (1991). Output effects of government purchases. *Journal of Political Economy* 89(6):1086-1121.
- Dickey, D.A & Fuller, W.A (1979). Distribution of the estimators for autoregressive time series with a unit root. *Journal of the American Statistical Association*. 74: 427–431.
- Fosu, O. A. & Magnus, F. J. (2006). Bounds testing approach to co-integration: An examination of foreign direct investment, trade openness and growth in Cote d'ivoire. *American Journal of Applied Sciences* 3 (11), 2079 – 2085.
- Hussain, N. (2016). *Examined the Impact of foreign aid to agriculture sector on agricultural productivity in developing countries in the context of second goal of SDGs*. A dissertation

- submitted to KDI School of Public Policy and Management in partial fulfillment of the requirements For the degree of Master of Development Policy.
- Igweze-Ekwunife, A. E. & Okpala, C. J. (2022). Impact of government expenditure on agricultural output in Nigeria. *International Journal of Research and Innovation in Social Science (IJRISS)*, VI(XII), 433 – 440.
- Iheke, O.R (2016). Remittances and the economy: The Nigerian experience. *Scientific Paper Series in Management, Economic Engineering in Agriculture and Rural Development*, 16(3):145-152.
- Iheke, O.R (2016). Remittances and the economy: The Nigerian experience. *Scientific Paper Series in Management, Economic Engineering in Agriculture and Rural Development*, 16(3):145-152.
- Ishola, S.A., Olaleye, S.O., Ajayi, E.O., and Femi, E (2013). Government Expenditure on the Agricultural Sector and Economic Growth in Nigeria. *Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences*, 8 (2): 62 – 67.
- Lawal, W.A. (2011). An analysis of government spending on agricultural sector and its contribution to gross domestic product in Nigeria. *International Journal of Business and Social Science*, 2(20), 244-250.
- Lipsey, R. E. (2001). Foreign direct investment and the operations of multinational firms: Concepts, history and data. *NBER Working Paper No. 8665*, Cambridge, UK.
- Lipsey, R.E. (2001). Foreign direct investment and the operations of multinational firms: Concepts, history and data, NBER Working Paper N° 8665, *Cambridge, MA; National Bureau of Economic Research (NBER)*.
- maputo declaration (2004). 4th summit of ACP heads of state and government maputo, Mozambique 23 and 24 June 2004.
- Mogues, T., Ayele, G., & Paulos, Z. (2008). The bang for the Birr: public expenditures and rural welfare in Ethiopia. IFPRI Research Report 160. *International Food Policy Research Institute*. Washington, D.C., USA.
- Nomor, A., & Udele, B. (2024). Government agricultural expenditure, agricultural output and economic growth in Nigeria: A structural vector autoregressive approach. *Journal of Economic and Social Research (JESR)* 10 (I), 244 – 263.
- Okorie, G. C; & Chikwendu, N. F. (2022). Impact of Nigerian agricultural expenditure on agricultural sector output. *Journal of Faculty of Management and Social Sciences* (10/1) 63-73.
- Onakoya, A. B., & Somoye R. C. (2013). The impact of public capital expenditure on economic growth in Nigeria. *Global Journal of Economics and Finance*, 2(1), 1-11.
- Pesaran, M. H., Shin, Y., & Smith, R. J. (2001). Bounds testing approaches to the analysis of level relationships. *Journal of Applied Econometrics*, 16: 289–326.
- Romer, P. M (1994). The origins of endogenous growth. *Journal of Economic Perspectives*. 8(1): 3–22.
- Romer, P. M. (1987a). Crazy explanations for the productivity slowdown. In Fischer, S.(ed.). *NBER Macroeconomics Annual*. Cambridge: MIT Press, 163–202.
- Romer, P. M., & Lucas, C. (1990). Are no-convexities important for understanding growth? *American Economic Review*, 80(2):97-103.

- Sikandar, F., Erokhin, V., Wang, H., Rehman, S. & Ivolga, A. (2021). The impact of foreign capital inflows on agriculture development and poverty reduction: Panel data analysis for developing countries. *Sustainability* 2021, 13, 3242. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su13063242>
- Udoh, E. (2011). An examination of public expenditure, private investment and agricultural sector growth in Nigeria: Bounds testing approach. *International Journal of Business and Social Science*, 2(13), 285-291.
- Verter, N., (2017). The impact of agricultural foreign aid on agriculture in Nigeria. *Bulg. J. Agric. Sci.*, 23 (5): 689–697.
- WDI (2024). World Bank World Development Indicators Database. Available at <http://data.worldbank.org/datacatalog/world-development-indicators>.
- Yaoming, Y. (2010). The relationship between foreign direct investment, trade openness and growth in Cote d' Ivoire. *International Journal of Business and Management* , 5 (7), 99-107.